

Search for "New Potential Pesticides" - Part VII

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A series of phenoxy acetyl 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl amides have been prepared with a view to test their insecticidal properties.

FUNGICIDAL, herbicidal properties of phenoxy acetic acids and their derivatives have been reported¹⁻³. Various 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazole and its many derivatives have also been reported to possess insecticidal, herbicidal and pesticidal properties⁴⁻⁷. Keeping these views in mind several amides have been synthesised with a view to study their insecticidal properties.

In all twentyfour amides have been synthesised according to the scheme given below :

Experimental

Preparation of 2-amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole :

A mixture of 0.2 mole of appropriate acid, 0.075 mole of thiosemicarbazide and 10 g. of H_2SO_4 was refluxed on a sand bath for two hours. Then the reaction mixture was poured into 40 g. ice H_2O and neutralised with 20 cc. 28% NH_4OH to give the desired compound. The compound was recrystallised from boiling water or dilute alcohol.

Substituted phenoxy acetyl 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl amides :

To a mixture of 0.01 mole of amino-thiadiazole^{8,9} in 15 ml. dry benzene and 0.02 mole of anhydrous potassium carbonate was added slowly a solution of 0.01 mole phenoxy acetyl chloride¹⁰⁻¹² in 15 ml. dry benzene. The solution was shaken 10-15 min and then refluxed on steam bath for 3-4 hours. Benzene was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the residue was washed several

TABLE I

S.No.	M.P. °C	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	Mol. formula	% of Nitrogen	
							Calc.	Found
1.	198	H	H	H	H	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.87	17.65
2.	194	H	H	Cl	H	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.61	15.72
3.	218	Cl	H	Cl	H	C ₁₀ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.86	13.78
4.	174	CH ₃	H	H	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.87	16.80
5.	212	H	CH ₃	H	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.87	16.94
6.	172	H	H	CH ₃	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.87	16.85
7.	223	H	H	H	CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.87	16.75
8.	245	H	H	Cl	CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	14.85	14.65
9.	250 d	Cl	H	Cl	CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.25	13.55
10.	236	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.97	16.11
11.	230	H	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.97	16.30
12.	223	H	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.97	15.85
13.	196	H	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.96	15.78
14.	234	H	H	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	14.14	13.96
15.	240 d	Cl	H	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	12.69	12.54
16.	189	CH ₃	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.16	15.44
17.	190	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.16	15.35
18.	221	H	H	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.16	14.96
19.	185	H	H	H	C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.16	14.86
20.	182	H	H	Cl	C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	13.50	13.76
21.	190	Cl	H	Cl	C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	12.17	11.98
22.	168	CH ₃	H	H	C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	14.43	14.23
23.	184	H	CH ₃	H	C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	14.43	14.68
24.	189	H	H	CH ₃	C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	14.43	14.62

times with cold water. Compounds were obtained in 70-85% yields and were crystallised from alcohol or DMF or a mixture of both.

All the melting points are uncorrected.

The insecticidal activity of these compounds will be communicated later on as it is under investigation.

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